
Scienxt Journal of Recent Trends in Semiconductors

Volume-2 // Issue-3 // Sept-Dec // Year-2024 // pp. 1-12

Systematic review on electrical vehicle charging technology development

***¹Mr. Mirajkar Ramkrishna Vasant**

¹Post Graduate Student, Rajarambapu Institute of Technology, Rajaramnagar, Islampur,
Sangli, Maharashtra, India

**Corresponding Author: Mr. Mirajkar Ramkrishna Vasant*

Abstract:

As the electrical vehicles (EV) sales are increasing day by day, a large amount of electrical mobility is having future. Now long range electrical vehicles are actually a reality on the transportation road. But, time consuming process of electrical vehicle charging and inconvenient process to charge electrical vehicles is becoming a hurdle. So customers willing to buy electrical mobility as an option for automobile are facing problems. This paper reviews the technology to charge electric vehicles, types of chargers used in different regional market and technology development to charge electric vehicles less time consuming, more efficiently and convenient.

Keywords:

EV, AC Charging, DC Charging, Inductive Charging- Static & Dynamic, Smart Charging.

1. Introduction:

Nowadays, number of electric vehicles are increasing in auto industry. Energy conservation and environment protection are major reasons for increase in sell of electrical vehicles. To make CO₂ neutral balance EV is important. The Government regulations promote use of electric vehicle's various models by companies. With respect to time, different models by company are available in market. The signal is clear that the gasoline vehicles will be replaced by electric vehicles. For the first time, the global sales of one million of new electric vehicles were numbered in 2017 Year. The annual passenger EV sales are expected to cross 10 million by Year 2025.

As electric charging network is increasing to provide EV drivers to access wide and reliable infrastructure, it is needed to be prepared to supply additional power required. The factor of convenient and fast charging is becoming a priority for consumers. The medium range 200 miles being provided by battery pack making the developments in poor range. With more than 350 miles range being provided by Year 2025. Several energy suppliers are launching electric charging solutions.

This paper is about how EV are charged, technology development in segments of charging. The automotive industry is profound on change. It isn't just product and technology that change. It is how people use the products and technology and experience the ownership of product. It is about to give consumers a better charging experience which is most convenient and efficient and less time consuming than what is being offered today.

The current methods to charge EV are described. Conductive AC, DC charging is explained in detail. The new technological developments are introduced. Static inductive charging, dynamic inductive charging, Battery swap and Smart charging technologies are described. Some examples of industry who are working on new technology in charging are explained and concluded with near future in charging technology.

2. Methods to charge an EV:

The main component in an EV is the battery pack inside it and needs to be charged from time to time. There are various ways to charge it. The three ways are –

- I. Conductive Charging
 - (i) AC
 - (ii) DC

II. Inductive Charge

III. Battery Swap

While Inductive charging is existed, it has still not been standardised. On the other hand, Battery Swap technology is something which we hope to have in the future. Each process is described in detail further.

3. Conductive charging:

3.1. Parts of AC Charger:

It is the simplest form where AC charging uses on-board charger to convert electricity from conventional AC grid (AC Power) to DC Power to charge traction battery. Cars have standardised vehicle inlet and charging cable is used to connect the vehicle connector to AC charging station. In some cases charging cable is permanently connected to charging station as well, similar to petrol pump. For safe and reliable charging process, there should be several essential components in AC charging station. The essential components are shown in power flow (Fig. 1) from charger to EV below. The moment the charging station and EV are connected, the charge controller in station communicates the information regarding the connectivity, fault condition and current limits of EV.

Figure. 1: Basic AC charging configuration

Safety interlocks are used to ensure a safe charging process and to stop charging in the event of a fault condition an improper connection between the EV and the charger. As the AC power is provided to the AC the on-board Charger has a rectifier which converts the AC power to DC power. Then the power control unit appropriately adjusts the voltage and the current of an AC/DC converter to control the charging power delivery to the battery. Since the power control unit is linked with the BMS (Battery management system) for controlling the battery charging. The BMS monitors the key battery operation parameters like the voltage, current and temperature. It then provides inputs to the power control unit to control the charging power delivered by the DC/DC converter. If the battery operating limits like the voltage or current are exceeded

the BMS triggers the protection circuit inside the on board charger, thereby isolating the battery if needed for its safe operation.

3.2. Types of AC Charger:

Due to the difference in AC voltage and frequency around the world, the EV industry has unfortunately not agreed on one specific AC connector, therefore depending upon the car brand and country, the shape, size and pin configuration vary in the connector. For example, in the USA, power is supplied using 120V, 60Hz, dual AC or 240 V, 60Hz, dual-phase AC. On the other hand in Europe, 230V, 50Hz, single-phase AC or 400 Hz three-phase AC is used. Due to these differences in voltages, the number of phases and frequency it leads to differences in chargers between the two regions. Generally, an AC connector has two or more larger pins to transmit power and a few smaller pins for the sake of communication. There are four types of AC connectors (Fig. 2) used globally.

Figure. 2: AC Charger types

1. **Type 1 Connector:** Used mostly in USA and Japan – Contains 2 pins for single phase AC – One pin for protective earth and 2 signal pins used for communication. The voltage rating is 120V – 240 V & Current up to 80 A
2. **Type 2 Connector:** Mostly used in Europe including European specification Tesla Cars. – The top row consists of 2 pins for communication, middle and lower row consists of five pins (three pins for three phase AC and two pins for neutral and protective earth) used for AC power transfer.
3. **Type 3 Connector:** Used in Europe but is being increasingly phased out by the Type 2 Connector.
4. **Tesla US Connector:** In the case of Tesla, they are proprietary connector – They use Type 2 connector in Europe. – Unlike other manufacturer Tesla uses the same connector

for both AC and DC charging. Maximum charging power of 17.2 kW when connected to 240 V AC outlet.

AC charging or Alternating Current charging is the most common type of charger and its advantage is that the battery can be recharged anywhere, where there is standard electric outlet.

3.3. Parts of DC Chargers:

DC chargers are designed to quickly charge the electric vehicles. They operate at level 3 charging powers with an output ranging between 50kW-350kW. DC chargers are implemented as an off-board charger rather than an on-board charger because with high power operation, the AC/DC converter, the DC/DC converter and the power control circuits become larger and more expensive, which makes it impractical to integrate it as an on board charger. Therefore to avoid taking up space within the vehicle they are set up as off-board chargers which can be shared by many users.

Figure. 3: Off-board DC Charger

The power flow for DC charging (Fig. 3) from the DC charger to the EV battery is initiated by converting the AC power, provided by the AC grid to DC power using a rectifier inside the DC charging station. Then the voltage and the current of a DC/DC converter is appropriately adjusted by the power control unit. This is done so that the variable DC power delivered to charge the battery is controlled. The protection circuits and the safety interlocks used to de-energize the EV connector and to stop the charging process whenever there is a fault condition or an improper connection between the charger and the EV. The BMS plays the key role of controlling the voltage, the current and communicating with the charging station and to operate circuits in case of an unsafe situation. For example, CAN (Control area network) and PLC (Power line communication) are used for the communication between the EV and the charger.

3.4. Types of DC Charger:

Figure. 4: DC Charger types

DC charger connectors are derived from the AC charger connector types, and are of five types used globally-

1. **CCS Combo 1:** Mainly used in the USA. The connector is derived from the AC type 1 connector. Two DC pins are added for fast charging, overall architecture remains the same as AC type 1 connector. Power line communication or PLC is used on the control pilot. CCS charger can deliver up to 350 Amps at a voltage of between 200 to 1000V giving a maximum power output of 350 kW.
2. **CCS Combo 2:** Mainly used in Europe. Derived from the AC Type 2 connectors. Two DC pins are added at the bottom of the connector for high power DC charging, they retain the rest AC Type 2 connector pins. Power line communication or PLC is used on the control pilot. CCS charger can deliver up to 350 Amps at a voltage of between 200 to 1000V giving a maximum power output of 350 kW.
3. **Chademo Connector:** Used globally for cars built by Japanese automakers. It is a type 4 EV connector. It uses the CAN (control area network) protocol in the communication pins. The voltage, current and power levels of chademo are 50-500V, up to 400A, thus providing a peak power of 200kW. In the future, it is expected that EV charging up to 1000V and 400kW will be facilitated through this connector.
4. **Tesla Charger Connector:** Tesla uses their own proprietary connector in the US, while the European variant uses the Type 2 connector with DC charging built-in. They use the same connector for both AC and DC charging. They offer DC charging up to 120kW; this is expected to increase in the future.
5. **DC Charger China GB/T Standard:** China's own DC connector. It uses the CAN bus for communication. Has five pins, two for low voltage auxiliary power and one for ground. It has four signal pins, 2 for proximity pilot and two for CAN communication. Maximum current 250A Nominal Voltage 750V or 1000V.

4. Future developments of EV charging:

The charging technologies are being constantly improved to provide a much better, hassle-free and less time-consuming EV charging experience. With the electric car market being established in many countries, key developments are being to ease the main drawback a customer thinks about- charging time/experience. The main technological developments we might experience in the future are-

4.1. Inductive Charging – Static Charging:

The concept behind inductive charging is the use of two electromagnetically linked coils. The primary coil is placed on the road surface, in a pad-like construction linked to the electricity network. The secondary coil is placed on the vehicle, ideally on the bottom of the car, at a safe distance from the passengers. Within the charging station, the AC is rectified and converted to a high-frequency AC power. Within the charger station; this high-frequency power is transferred to the EV side by induction. The main aim behind incorporating the wireless charging method in EVs is to make less mess than conductive charging since it has no cable, hence is more convenient. For self-driving cars, wireless communication can take care of everything, no plug behavior needed. Witricity Corporation, an American company that works on wireless charging technology which is just as efficient as conductive chargers aim to introduce wirelessly charged EVs and PHEVs (Plugin Hybrid Electric Vehicles) over the course of next three to four years. One of the big impediments to broad adoption of electric vehicles is just the frustration of the bulky cables and having to remember to plugin. Witricity Corporation aims to take this clumsy charging process out of the day to day lives of the people and provide technology with no user intervention at all. Just park your EV and it charges on its own. Wireless charging is a key enabler to the broad adoption of electric vehicles. They also focused on standardization of their technology making it interoperable from one automaker to another by working closely with almost all of the global automakers, thereby making its technology more practical to use in future.

4.2. Inductive Charging - Dynamic Charging:

There is another way to charge a car wirelessly- the dynamic charging, which is similar to static inductive charging. The energy transfer from the charger to the car is through magnetic coupling. Coils connected to electric cables that are used to provide power are buried in the road. The coils produce an electromagnetic field which is picked up by the

vehicles driving over them which is converted into electricity to charge the cars. The advantages of inductive dynamic charging are that it provides a low stand in charging time for customers. The battery size can be smaller as the battery pack can be charged regularly on the road. The main barriers of this technology are related to power transfer efficiency, as foreign objects on the road, abrasion of the surface of the road, and the coil structure changes inside the road-building materials may impact the features of the coil and reduce the power transfer efficiency.

Qualcomm Technologies, Inc. (QTI), one of the few companies working on dynamic wireless charging has developed a technology known as “Qualcomm Halo” intending to provide a simple and efficient way to charge electric vehicles. QTI’s Dynamic electric vehicle charging (DEVC) system is capable of charging an EV dynamically at, and above 100 km/h with 20 kW. DEVC technology was a result of a research undertaken at Qualcomm’s Auckland facility where the concept had been proven at low speed, the original objective of the project was to demonstrate how WEVC applies to dynamic charging. So far the dynamic inductive charging technology is still under the experimental stage due to many challenges to standardize it. These are –

1. Different ground clearances, car size and power level that could lead to sub-optimal operations.
2. Choosing a universal high- performance coil-type for dynamic charging is a challenge.
3. Real-time coil misalignment for different types of cars is hard to estimate.

Hence this technology is still far away from being commercialized.

5. Battery swap technology:

As the name suggests, this technology works on the basis of switching out the depleted battery and replacing the same battery with a fully charged battery. It involves driving into the battery switching bay, which through an automated process will position the vehicle and switch out the current battery and replace it with fully charged battery. The depleted batteries are then charged in the station for later deployment. The advantage of a battery swap technology is that it eliminates range anxiety and is just like refilling a tank, quick and easy. On paper, this technology has a lot of advantages but to get market acceptance would be a real challenge for such a technology, mainly because of the following reasons –

1. A standardized battery would be required across all auto manufacturers to practically use this technology.
2. It would be difficult for the consumers to accept a battery which they don't own and having to change the vehicle battery.
3. There should be a foolproof way to estimate the state of health of a battery and analyze the usage pattern.
4. The constant connection between the battery and the vehicle would need to be made and broken each time a battery is swapped. The electrical connection between the battery and the vehicle carries a very high current which causes a major safety concern for the customer, as every time a swap is done it will be because wear and degradation at the key link between the two components and at worst has the potential to cause a massive discharge.

6. Smart charging:

With our lives increasingly being heavily dependent on Electricity including electric vehicles, to use it effectively and efficiently will be very crucial in the future. Smart charging is a series of intelligent functionalities to control the EV charging power in order to create a flexible, sustainable, low cost, and efficient charging environment. Innovative technologies can help us manage how we use energy more efficiently and balance the demand on the grid. Analyzing the daily peaks and troughs in the energy demand, future electric charging solutions are being developed to optimize the use and provide stored energy back to the grid. Vehicle to grid charging and smart charging (also known as V2G) are such two technologies that can play a vital role in this act of balancing.

Shell, a global group of energy and petrochemicals, has launched a smart EV charging service including tariff and charger. Shell- owned New Motion will be offering a charger capable of providing 7 kW of power, charging a typical EV in five hours. It will be powered by 100% renewable energy since Shell switched to 100% renewable last year as it rebranded. The company also provides a shell recharge app through which customers can have access to 155,000 charge points in over 5 countries. New Motions charge card and app offer access to the largest charging network of Europe, which is expanding every day.

7. Conclusion:

The way we transmit power to charge our electric vehicles might change drastically in the upcoming years, which will indirectly help in the broad adoption of EVs. Starting from the different charger types used in the various regions of the world to working on wireless and battery swap technology, these initiatives in future development will immediately increase the convenience of owning an EV. The main advantage of owning an electric-powered vehicle is the feature of electricity to be used as a commodity since the whole world has moved on to electrification one can use its EV as a powerhouse and charge other devices during an emergency by using the V2G technology. Since an EV can be charged anywhere, the option to charge an EV while moving is also something tech companies have been working on to make the ownership experience of an EV more or as convenient as gasoline-powered cars. With many roadblocks to practical and global adoption of these future charging technologies, the fact that developments are being constantly made by companies and in some cases, the new technology is also being commercially available in some heavily EV dominated auto markets like the battery swap technology in China, shows us the scope of a future where the traditional charging methods being used in the current times will soon fade out as our auto industry gets increasingly electrified on a global scale. In conclusion, there is still a long way to go, to charge the battery of an EV in a more convenient, efficient and stable manner.

8. References:

- (1) Anon., "Electric Vehicle Market by Vehicle (Passenger Cars & Commercial Vehicles), Vehicle Class (Mid-priced & Luxury), Propulsion (BEV, PHEV FCEV), EV Sales (OEMs/Models) Charging Station (Normal & Super) & Region - Global Forecast to 2030," Markets and Markets,. Rep: AT 4907, June 2019. Available: <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/electric-vehicle-market-209371461.html>
- (2) M. Agrawal, M.S. Rajapatel. (2020, Jan). "Global Perspective on Electric Vehicle 2020. *International Journal of Engineering Research and technology* Available : <https://www.ijert.org/research/global-perspective-on-electric-vehicle-2020IJERTV9IS010005.pdf>
- (3) Alice. Grundy. (2020, Feb. 20). *Shell Energy launches EV charging bundle offering*

- 2,000 miles free charging Available: <https://www.current-news.co.uk/news/shell-energy-launches-ev-charging-bundle-offering-2-000-miles-free-charging>
- (4) Amsterdam Roundtable Foundation and McKinsey & Company The Netherlands, “Electric vehicles in Europe: Gearing up for a new phase?,” McKinsey & Company , Netherlands , April 1, 2014. Available: <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/europe/electric-vehicles-in-europe-gearing-up-for-a-new-phase>
- (5) Nio. (2020, Jun. 29). *A Brief History of Battery Swapping* [Online]. Available <https://www.nio.com/blog/brief-history-battery-swapping>
- (6) Qualcomm. (2017, May.18.). *From wireless to dynamic electric vehicle charging: The evolution of Qualcomm Halo*, Available: <https://www.qualcomm.com/news/onq/2017/05/18/wireless-dynamic-ev-charging-evolution-qualcomm-halo>
- (7) Fred Lambert.(2020,Jun,2.).*Nio Might Have Figured Out Battery Swap For Electric Cars As It Completes 500,000 Swaps* [Online]. Available:<https://electrek.co/2020/06/02/nio-battery-swap-electric-cars-completes-500000-swaps/>
- (8) Shell.(2020) *Electric Vehicle Charging* [Online]. Available: <https://www.shell.com/energy-and-innovation/new-energies/electric-vehicle-charging.html>
- (9) Prof. Dr. Pavol Bauer, Dr Gautham Ram Chandra Mouli (Delft University of Technology). *Electric Cars: Technology* Available:<https://courses.edx.org/courses/coursev1:DelftX+eCARS2x+3T2019/course/>
- (10) International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology, (IJERT), Online available <http://ijert.org>